

Newly Registered breeds of Livestock and Poultry

Dr. G.Raju^{*1}, Dr. A. Deepika²

^{*1}M.V.Sc Department of Veterinary Gynaecology and Obstetrics, PVNR TVU, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad- 500030 Telangana, India

²M.V.Sc, Department of Veterinary Medicine, PVNR TVU, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad- 500030 Telangana, India

P.V. Narsimha Rao Telangana State Veterinary University, Telangana-500030

Total number of indigenous animal breeds are now 53 for cattle, 20 for buffalo, 39 for goat, 45 for sheep, 8 for horses & ponies, 9 for camel, 14 for pig, 3 for donkey, 3 for dog, 1 for yak, 20 for chicken, 3 for duck, and 1 for geese. The National Bureau of Animal Genetic Resources also registered Frieswal cattle as a first synthetic breed in the country.

Newly registered breeds

1. Aravali: Aravali is a dual-purpose chicken breed that is raised for both meat and eggs. They are known for their heat tolerance and broodiness.

Appearance:

- Male Aravali chickens have birchen plumage.
- Female Aravali chickens have shafty and laced plumage.
- Average annual egg production is 72 eggs.
- Excellent heat tolerance.
- Very good broodiness hatchability and mothering ability.
- Found in Banaskantha, Sabarkantha, Aravalli and Mahisagar districts of Gujarat State.

2. Andamani Duck: Andamani duck is a dual-purpose breed, mainly distributed in Nimbudera to Diglipur region of Andaman & Nicobar Islands

Appearance:

- They are medium sized ducks with features such as a comparatively longer neck a yellowish bill with a black tip black skin a white band around the neck and a shorter shank as compared to other indigenous ducks.
 - Average adult body weight for drake is 1406 gm.
 - Average annual egg production is 266 eggs.

3. Anjori goat: It is used for meat purpose. It is distributed in Raipur, Durg, Rajnandgaon, Kanker, Dhamtari, Mahasamund districts of Chhattisgarh state. **Appearance:**

- It is a medium sized goat.
- Majority of animals are brown in colour.
- It is hardy and well adapted to the local climate.

4. Andamani goat: It is reared for meat purpose in the Middle and North Andaman districts of Andaman

- These goats are medium to short in stature have a compact body and are mostly black in colour.
- Ears are flat and leaf-like, medium sized and drooping.
- Both sexes have small horns, curved upward and backward.
- The tail is medium in length and curved upward.
- The body weight at 12 months of age varies from 14 to 19 kg.

& Nicobar Islands.

Appearance:

5. Bhimthadi horse: It is distributed in Pune, Solapur, Satara and Ahmadnagar district of Maharashtra.

Appearance:

- The average height of stallion is about 130 cm and of mare is 128 cm.
- Bhimthadi horses are mainly used for transportation of household material during migration of the

pastoralist people.

6. Andamani pig: It is a native to the islands of Andaman & Nicobar and mainly reared for meat (pork).

Appearance:

- These pigs are sturdy, medium in size and black (mostly) or brownish in colour.
- Neck and back portion hairs are very thick as well as long, whereas hairs on the sides and flank regions are shorter and thinner, respectively.
- The most commonly observed feature is the slightly downward arch or curvature of the back (low back).
- They attain a body weight of 60-75kg for males and 55-65kg for females at 1 year of age under field conditions.
- Litter size at farrowing ranges from 6-13. They are fast runners and evolved to thrive under low- input management system.

- 7. Macherla sheep:** It is meat purpose sheep breed of Gunatur, Krishna and Prakasam district of Andhra Pradesh and nearby region of Telangana.

Appearance:

- It is medium to large in size. Adults' rams weigh 38-69 kg and ewes weigh 25-60 kg.
- Coat colour is white with large brown or black patches on the body, face and legs.
- Rams are horned, while ewes are polled.
- Ears are leafy or semi- drooping, medium to large in size.
- Wattles are pendulous lobules hanging from the throat region in both males and females.
- Very small and thin tail.

- 8. Frieswal:** It is synthetic dairy cattle with Sahiwal (37.5) and Holstein Friesian (62.5) inheritance, developed by ICAR-Central Institute for Research on Cattle, Meerut. This breed is high milk production and acclimatized to agro-climatic regions of the country.

Appearance:

- Black and white body colour in varying proportions.
- Black skin, followed by black and brown.
- Black muzzle, black hooves and white tail switch.
- Medium dewlap and small naval flap.

